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TEXT MINING: OPEN SOURCE TOKENIZATION TOOLS – AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Text mining is the process of extracting interesting and non-trivial knowledge or information from unstructured text data. Text mining is the multidisciplinary field which draws on data mining, machine learning, information retrieval, computational linguistics and statistics. Important text mining processes are information extraction, information retrieval, natural language processing, text classification, content analysis and text clustering. All these processes are required to complete the preprocessing step before doing their intended task. Pre-processing significantly reduces the size of the input text documents and the actions involved in this step are sentence boundary determination, natural language specific stop-word elimination, tokenization and stemming. Among this, the most essential and important action is the tokenization. Tokenization helps to divide the textual information into individual words. For performing tokenization process, there are many open source tools are available. The main objective of this work is to analyze the performance of the seven open source tokenization tools. For this comparative analysis, we have taken Nlpdotnet Tokenizer, Mila Tokenizer, NLTK Word Tokenize, TextBlob Word Tokenize, MBSP Word Tokenize, Pattern Word Tokenize and Word Tokenization with Python NLTK. Based on the results, we observed that the Nlpdotnet Tokenizer tool performance is better than other tools.

KEYWORDS:

Text Mining, Preprocessing, Tokenization, machine learning, NLP

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**PREDICTION OF LUNG CANCER USING IMAGE PROCESSING
TECHNIQUES: A REVIEW**

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ABSTRACT

Prediction of lung cancer is most challenging problem due to structure of cancer cell, where most of the cells are overlapped each other. The image processing techniques are mostly used for prediction of lung cancer and also for early detection and treatment to prevent the lung cancer. To predict the lung cancer various features are extracted from the images therefore, pattern recognition based approaches are useful to predict the lung cancer. Here, a comprehensive review for the prediction of lung cancer by previous researcher using image processing techniques is presented. The summary for the prediction of lung cancer by previous researcher using image processing techniques is also presented.

KEYWORDS:

Classification, lung cancer, accuracy, image processing techniques

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WEB SPAM CLASSIFICATION USING SUPERVISED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

Due to the rapid growth in technology employed by the spammers, there is a need of classifiers that are more efficient, generic and highly adaptive. Neural Network based technologies have high ability of adaption as well as generalization. As per our knowledge, very little work has been done in this field using neural network. We present this paper to fill this gap. This paper evaluates performance of three supervised learning algorithms of artificial neural network by creating classifiers for the complex problem of latest web spam pattern classification. These algorithms are Conjugate Gradient algorithm, Resilient Backpropagation learning, and Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Web spam, artificial neural network, back-propagation algorithms, Conjugate Gradient, Resilient Backpropagation, Levenberg-Marquardt, Web spam classification

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AUTOMATIC UNSUPERVISED DATA CLASSIFICATION USING JAYA EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we attempt to solve an automatic clustering problem by optimizing multiple objectives such as automatic k-determination and a set of cluster validity indices concurrently. The proposed automatic clustering technique uses the most recent optimization algorithm Jaya as an underlying optimization stratagem. This evolutionary technique always aims to attain global best solution rather than a local best solution in larger datasets. The explorations and exploitations imposed on the proposed work results to detect the number of automatic clusters, appropriate partitioning present in data sets and mere optimal values towards CVIs frontiers. Twelve datasets of different intricacy are used to endorse the performance of aimed algorithm. The experiments lay bare that the conjectural advantages of multi objective clustering optimized with evolutionary approaches decipher into realistic and scalable performance paybacks.

KEYWORDS

Multi objective optimization, evolutionary clustering, automatic clustering, cluster validity indexes, Jaya evolutionary algorithm.

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**A LITERATURE SURVEY ON RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM BASED ON
SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS**

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ABSTRACT

Recommender systems have grown to be a critical research subject after the emergence of the first paper on collaborative filtering in the Nineties. Despite the fact that educational studies on recommender systems, has extended extensively over the last 10 years, there are deficiencies in the complete literature evaluation and classification of that research. Because of this, we reviewed articles on recommender structures, and then classified those based on sentiment analysis. The articles are categorized into three techniques of recommender system, i.e.; collaborative filtering (CF), content based and context based. We have tried to find out the research papers related to sentimental analysis based recommender system. To classify research done by authors in this field, we have shown different approaches of recommender system based on sentimental analysis with the help of tables. Our studies give statistics, approximately trends in recommender structures research, and gives practitioners and researchers with perception and destiny route on the recommender system using sentimental analysis. We hope that this paper enables all and sundry who is interested in recommender systems research with insight for destiny.

KEYWORDS

Recommender systems; Literature review, Sentimental analysis

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**MACHINE LEARNING SYSTEMS BASED ON XGBOOST AND MLP
NEURAL NETWORK APPLIED IN SATELLITE LITHIUM-ION
BATTERY SETS IMPEDANCE ESTIMATION**

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the internal impedance of the lithium-ion battery pack (important measure of the degradation level of the batteries) is estimated by means of machine learning systems based on supervised learning techniques MLP - Multi Layer Perceptron - neural network and xgBoost - Gradient Tree Boosting. Therefore, characteristics of the electric power system, in which the battery pack is inserted, are extracted and used in the construction of supervised models through the application of two different techniques based on Gradient Tree Boosting and Multi Layer Perceptron neural network. Finally, with the application of statistical validation techniques, the accuracy of both models are calculated and used for the comparison between them and the feasibility analysis regarding the use of such models in real systems.

KEYWORDS

Lithium-ion battery, Internal impedance, State of charge, Multi Layer Perceptron, Gradient Tree Boosting, xgBoost

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A FUZZY BASED CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR CAREER COUNSELLING

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ABSTRACT

Career guidance for students, particularly in rural areas is a challenging issue in India. In the present era of digitalization, there is a need of an automated system that can analyze a student for his/her capabilities, suggest a career and provide related information. Keeping in mind the requirement, the present paper is an effort in this direction. In this paper, a fuzzy based conceptual framework has been suggested. It has two parts; in the first part a students will be analyzed for his/her capabilities and in the second part the available courses, job aspects related to their capabilities will be suggested. To analyze a student, marks in various subject in 10+2 standards and vocational interest in different fields have been considered and fuzzy sets have been formed. On example basis, fuzzy inference rules have been framed for analyzing the abilities in engineering, medical and hospitality fields only. In second part, concept of composition of relations has been used to suggest the related courses and jobs.

KEYWORDS

Career Counselling, Fuzzy sets, Fuzzy inference rules, compositions of relations

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CRYPTANALYSIS OF KEY EXCHANGE METHOD USING COMPUTATIONAL INTELLIGENCE GUIDED MULTILAYER PERCEPTRON IN WIRELESS COMMUNICATION (CKEMLP)

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a cryptanalysis of key exchange method using multilayer perceptron (CKEMLP) has been proposed in wireless communication of data/information. In this proposed CKEMLP technique both sender and receiver uses an identical multilayer perceptrons for synchronization between them. After achieving the full synchronization weights vectors of both the parties' becomes identical and this identical weight vector is used as a secret session key for encryption/decryption. Different types of possible attacks during synchronization phase are introduced in this paper. Among different types of attacks some of them can be easily prevented by increasing the synaptic depth L . But few attacks are also there which has a great success rate.

KEYWORDS

Cryptanalysis, Encryption, Wireless Communication

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NEW DECISION TREE METHOD FOR DATA MINING IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Today, enormous amount of data is collected in medical databases. These databases may contain valuable information encapsulated in nontrivial relationships among symptoms and diagnoses. Extracting such dependencies from historical data is much easier to done by using medical systems. Such knowledge can be used in future medical decision making. In this paper, a new algorithm based on C4.5 to mind data for medince applications proposed and then it is evaluated against two datasets and C4.5 algorithm in terms of accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Medicine, Classification, Decision Tree, ID3, C4.5

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LEARNING STRATEGY WITH GROUPS ON PAGE BASED STUDENTS' PROFILES

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ABSTRACT

Most of students desire to know about their knowledge level to perfect their exams. In learning environment the fields of study overwhelm on page with collaboration or cooperation. Students can do their exercises either individually or collaboratively with their peers. The system provides the guidelines for students' learning system about interest fields as Java in this system. Especially the system feedbacks information about exam to know their grades without teachers. The participants who answered the exam can discuss with each others because of sharing e mail and list of them.

KEYWORDS

Collaboration, Grade, Learning, Profiles, Feedback

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